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ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF THE SECURITIES MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR CAPITAL RAISING IN THIS MARKET

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Abstract: *Currently, securities are considered one of the most versatile financial instruments. Securities, as an object of civil rights, closely contribute to the development of commodity-money relations and the development of the country's economy. Previously, in the conditions of a planned economy, certain types of securities were used in property relations (bonds, lottery tickets, bills of exchange in foreign trade). The transition of the economy to a market economy and the formation of the securities market have necessitated the reconstruction of the types of securities and the creation of new ones. In turn, the study of all the opportunities offered by this market has also necessitated the analysis of modern methods of raising capital in this market.*

Keywords: *Securities, economy, market, capital.*

INTRODUCTION

Despite the youth of the Uzbek stock market, its history is marked by specific transactions in options and futures. Some option contracts were concluded in 1992 in the stock department of the Tashkent Stock Exchange. The Regulation on the option of the State Property Committee for the sale of state-owned shares, as well as shares intended for free sale and sale to partners, was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic on October 24, 1994 under No. 110, in accordance with which the sale of shares of the authorized capital of enterprises undergoing privatization (future shares) was carried out.¹ According to the Regulation, options on shares Over-the-counter auctions of option contracts were held, the initial prices of the premiums for which amounted to approximately 40 percent of the nominal value of the package of shares of the enterprise's management fund put up for sale. The winner of the auction transaction acquired the right to purchase a share of the company's mutual fund, but in the form of securities, at a fixed (usually nominal) price agreed upon in the contract after they were put into circulation by the issuer, or to withdraw from the transaction. In 1995, the Tashkent Regional Department of the State Property Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange approved a regulation on futures contracts for the sale of state property of the Tashkent Regional

State Property Department, as well as shares intended for free sale. The system of selling state property, as well as shares intended for free sale and sale to partners, on the basis of futures contracts was aimed at accelerating the privatization process, activating the stock market, and creating conditions for the formation of market prices for securities based on the sale price. In accordance with the Regulation, a futures contract for state property of enterprises undergoing privatization, as well as shares intended for free sale and sale to partners (futures contract of the Tashkent regional state property department) is a bilateral contract for the purchase of a share of state property at a guaranteed (fixed) price within a certain period of time or on a certain future date, provided the obligation. In Uzbekistan, futures transactions can only be carried out on stock exchanges.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Securities and Stock Exchanges" adopted on September 2, 1993, "Securities are documents confirming property rights or debt relations between the person who holds them and their owner, the payment of income in the form of dividends or interest, as well as the possibility of transferring the rights arising from these documents to another person." The second stage of the economic reforms being implemented in our country was a new stage in the development of the securities market. Therefore, serious attention is now being paid to the securities market. In particular, the organization of the secondary market has begun. In order to rapidly organize the infrastructure of the stock market, investment companies and funds, clearing houses and stock shops, advertising firms, and private equity funds (PIFs) were formed.

In January 1992, the Fund Department of the Tashkent Stock Exchange became the first in the republic to start regular trading in securities. In the same year, the turnover of the Fund Department of the Tashkent Stock Exchange in securities transactions amounted to 26 million rubles, which was comparable to similar indicators of Russian stock exchanges. In its activities, the stock exchange is guided by the legislative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the stock exchange charter, and the rules for carrying out work related to securities. The stock exchange (stock department of a stock exchange or currency exchange) is registered in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is licensed by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan to conduct stock exchange activities in securities. An organization that has not obtained a license to conduct securities exchange activities is not entitled to engage in such activities. Fund departments may be organized as independent structural divisions and non-independent structural divisions on stock exchanges and currency exchanges. Fund departments must comply with all requirements imposed on stock exchanges in their activities. Legal entities and individuals who have a permit (license) granting the right to conduct securities transactions may become founders of a stock exchange. Legal entities and individuals who have purchased a brokerage position on the stock exchange, including foreign legal entities and individuals, may become members of a stock exchange (stock department of a commodity or currency exchange). The number of members of the stock exchange is determined by the governing bodies of the exchange, their officials and specialists, who are not entitled to be members of the stock exchange. (The words were deleted in the amendment based on Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 7 dated September 22, 2005) Stock exchange members are allowed to trade in securities if they have licenses to conduct transactions and have received the status of an investment institution. An individual who has purchased a brokerage position may engage in trading after registering it with local government

bodies and opening a bank account. The rules for stock exchange operations in securities are approved by the top management of the exchange.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The need to use optimal methods for assessing the effectiveness of securities activities as a research methodology was justified. Examples of contracts, reports, orders and notifications used in the implementation of securities transactions, as well as other exchange-related documents. The Stock Exchange independently develops and approves the procedure for concluding transactions during the exchange trading period, verifying transactions and making settlements on their basis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Stock exchanges and fund departments operate on the basis of the regulations and business rules for the implementation of securities transactions, agreed with the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Stock Exchange Regulation (Regulation on the Fund Department). Transactions on the stock exchange can be carried out by its members.

Monetary support for the activities of the stock exchange:

- sale of stock exchange shares and units;
- sale of brokerage positions on the stock exchange;
- membership fees paid regularly by members of the stock exchange;
- fees charged for the registration of stock exchange transactions;
- commissions charged for intermediation in securities transactions;
- may be carried out at the expense of income from the provision of information services and other related services provided by the stock exchange.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a special center was established under the Committee for Management of State Property and Support of Entrepreneurship in the building of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (March 30, 1996) to monitor and control the activities of the securities market.

The decisions of the Center within the scope of its activities, strictly observing the forms of ownership, are mandatory for business associations, enterprises and organizations, as well as citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign states. In countries with relatively large territories, regional or local securities markets are usually formed. In Uzbekistan, for example, the local securities markets were established with the aim of delegating securities trading to the discretion of the administrative-territorial structures consisting of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent, and 12 regions. Each of these regions has government departments, branches of stock exchanges, and general and specialized infrastructure of the securities market. Regardless of the common principles of organization, regional markets differ from each other in the level of development of the economy as a whole, the affiliation of issuers to a particular industry, the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of issuers and potential investors, the development of infrastructure, the activity of professional participants, and, in turn, the volume of transactions with securities. Naturally, for example, the owners of securities issued in the Surkhandarya region are mainly local organizations and citizens. Thus, when transferring funds from farms and the population within the region, a limited circulation is allowed, relative to consumption. In this regard, we can talk about the securities markets formed in the city of Tashkent, Andijan region, the Republic of

Karakalpakstan, and the Khorezm regions, which differ from each other in the above-mentioned characteristics. However, it should always be remembered that these markets are closely interconnected, regulated and managed by a single center, and have a common legal framework for all of them, forming a single stock market of Uzbekistan.

Above, we have familiarized ourselves with the securities market of Uzbekistan in detail, and now let us dwell on the prospects for applying the experience of the securities markets of Great Britain and the USA in these conditions. In order to improve the development and regulation of the Uzbek securities market, it would be appropriate to apply the following elements of the British and American systems:

- It is necessary to introduce the British system of risk mitigation (Debt Management Office) and incentive mechanisms;
- The emerging new securities market is still not saturated, and it is necessary to expand the sector through the introduction of world experience and technological modernization;
- To organize special brokers listed on the leading US stock exchanges. This will help to control the exchange;
- It is necessary to organize a special committee for the development of the securities market;
- It is necessary to expand the structure of the securities market and divide it into chambers and committees;
- It is necessary to transform market participants into independent brokers working with banks, like in Great Britain.

If the above methods are used, we believe that the current problems in the securities market can be solved. Of course, implementing this step by step would be in the best interests of all parties.

Currently, the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange is considered the main trading platform of the securities market of our country, where trades in various securities are carried out.

Figure 1. Trading turnover of the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange in 2023.

During 2023, the volume of transactions in more than 99 billion securities of 103 issuers amounted to 578.15 billion soums. The highest level of transaction volume occurred in August, exceeding 100 billion soums; the minimum was recorded in April - during the lockdown in the republic, transactions amounted to 773 million soums. Over the year, the number of transactions for all sites exceeded 36 thousand. The largest number of transactions was concluded in January - 4,477 transactions, which exceeded the average monthly number of transactions for 2023 by more than 49 percent. The lowest number of transactions was recorded in April - only 2,336. The primary securities market is a market for the implementation of the issue and primary placement of securities, that is, the initial sale of securities by the issuer or its representative to a primary investor.

In particular, the level of free circulation of securities in the secondary market is growing year by year. In 2020, its turnover decreased by 1.3 times compared to 2011.

Figure 2. Trading turnover of the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange in 2020

As of December 31, 2020, there were 145 joint-stock companies with a market capitalization of 54.80 trillion soums on the list of stock exchange quotations of the Tashkent Stock Exchange. In mid-April, the capitalization of the stock exchange market reached its minimum level in 2020 and approached the figure of 49 trillion soums. This decline in market capitalization began in February, mainly due to the delisting of 18 joint-stock companies, most of which did not meet the requirements of the Regulation on the list of stock exchange quotations. Then, over the next 5 months, the capitalization of the stock exchange market showed an average level of 50 trillion soums.

According to the results of stock market trading in 2023, the share of the volume of joint placement of securities in the total stock market turnover was 50.9% or 86.8 billion soums. Thus, the total volume of stock market turnover shows the following:

Volume of joint placement:

- issue of additional shares - 59.3 billion soums;
- corporate bonds - 34.4 billion soums. Secondary market turnover:
- stocks - 51.2 billion soums;
- corporate bonds - 24.5 billion soums.

The investment attractiveness of securities in the joint placement of securities on the Tashkent Stock Exchange and their circulation on the secondary market can be analyzed as follows: As of the end of 2023, the main part of the funds raised through the joint placement of shares and bonds issued by joint-stock companies for the first time will be represented by the share of securities of commercial banks, i.e., the share of shares issued in general 67.8% of the volume of issues. Among the issuers that have successfully placed their additional issues through the stock exchange, one can also include industrial enterprises - 25.8% and trade enterprises - 6.4%. Commercial banks' securities also occupy a high position in the secondary market, accounting for 65.4% of the total turnover of the secondary market. In addition, interest in securities of industrial enterprises in the secondary market is also growing - 19.4%.

In addition, the volume of transactions concluded with securities of enterprises in the industrial sector accounted for 21.6% of the total exchange turnover (46.0 billion soums).

The composition of the main sectors of the economy in the stock exchange turnover in 2023 is as follows:

- the share of the financial sector in the total exchange turnover is 55.9% or 95.4 billion soums, including banks - 51.6% or 88.1 billion soums, insurance companies - 2.1% or 3.6 billion soums and leasing companies - 2.2% or 3.7 billion soums;
- the share of the industrial sector in the total stock market turnover - 29.3% or 49.9 billion soums;
- the share of the construction sector - 2.1% or 3.5 billion soums;

Figure 3. Composition of economic sectors in the trading turnover of the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange.

One of the factors that has stimulated the activity of the stock exchange is the expansion of the number of potential investors. In today's globalization process, the opportunity to quickly make a profit through the trading of securities is expanding compared to previous years. World experience shows that investments in securities bring more benefits than investments in some other areas and can provide reliable protection against inflation. Undoubtedly, in our country, too, a class of investors is forming who are increasing their activity in the securities market and understand that they can own the assets of joint-stock companies by purchasing their shares. In order to attract a wider flow of investors to the stock market, the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent" has implemented a number of measures to further improve the system of exchange transaction technologies and minimize transaction costs for trading participants. In particular, the amount of fees for the provision of stock exchange services has been reduced by almost half since April.

When analyzing the structure of the stock exchange market by investor category, the main part of which is made up of small businesses and private entrepreneurs, the amount of investments directed by legal entities into securities of all sectors of the economy is 158.7 billion soums, or 93% of the total exchange turnover. The share of individuals in the total exchange turnover in 2023 was 7%, or 11.9 billion soums.

Figure 4. The composition of investors in the trading turnover of the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange.

One of the main goals of the stock exchange today is to attract financially stable and liquid joint-stock companies in our republic to listing. The inclusion of joint-stock companies in the official stock exchange listing indicates a certain level of reliability and financial stability of these companies, and the constant disclosure of information about them increases investors' confidence in investing.

In addition, the listing of joint-stock companies on the stock exchange creates broad opportunities for their integration into international stock markets, that is, foreign investors consider the shares of companies listed first as a priority. Foreign stock exchanges are mainly interested in trading in securities belonging to joint-stock companies listed on the stock exchange of their own country.

In order to attract joint-stock companies to the exchange listing, the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange has introduced relevant changes to the current listing procedures, namely, the process of listing joint-stock companies has been simplified and the amount of listing fees has been revised.

The measures taken by the stock exchange to attract joint-stock companies to listing have borne fruit, including the fact that in 2020 the number of listed companies was 4, while by the end of 2023 the number of joint-stock companies listed on the exchange was 113. The list of listed companies includes commercial banks, insurance companies, oil and gas industry, light industry, construction materials processing and processing, agro-industrial complex, energy and metallurgy, as well as other enterprises.

Today, 17 of the joint-stock companies listed on the exchange belong to the category “A”, which is considered an oily category, 20 to the category “B”, and 76 joint-stock companies to the category “C”.

Thus, joint-stock companies that meet the requirements of category “C” constitute a significant majority, that is, the authorized capital of these joint-stock companies is an amount equivalent to 400,000 (four hundred thousand) US dollars at the rate established by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the date of state registration of the company, and the results of the last two financial years are positive. shows.

In recent years, the share of transactions with shares of listed companies in the total stock exchange turnover has been growing significantly. In 2018, this indicator amounted to 3.3%, but by the end of 2023 it amounted to 49.6%.

Another important advantage of joint-stock companies listed on the stock exchange is that the listed securities are quoted without any doubts, which creates a market mechanism for the formation of the price of these shares, as well as the opportunity to determine the true market price of shares, which in turn leads to an increase in their capitalization.

As of December 31, 2023, the market capitalization of shares of joint-stock companies included in the official listing of the exchange amounted to 5448.9 billion soums. The logical continuation of the strategy of expanding the range of services of the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent" is the development of the repo market in our country. REPO transactions are a popular method of borrowing funds by pledging securities. Securities belonging to a client can not only bring benefits, but can also be used as an effective tool that can instantly attract credit funds.

Figure 5. Turnover structure of listed companies by months of 2023.

In 2023, the exchange's mobile REPO trading floor conducted 20 first-stage REPO transactions worth 4.8 billion soums with shares of 10 issuers and 8 second-stage REPO transactions worth 2.2 billion soums with shares of 7 issuers.

In total, 332 REPO transactions involving shares of 47 issuers have been carried out since 2020. The volume of transactions in the first stage amounted to 40.9 billion soums, while in the second stage it amounted to 34.9 billion soums. The total volume of trading on the exchange with REPO transactions amounted to 75.8 billion soums.

CONCLUSION

In general, it should be emphasized once again that concluding a REPO transaction is beneficial for both the REPO initiator and its acceptor (creditor). Its simplicity and reliability make the process attractive for financial market participants and attract a wider range of investors to conclude such transactions.

In the current context of economic reforms, the development of the securities market that is being formed in our country and the need to increase the importance of corporate structures are also considered an important issue in the development of the country's economy. We can make the following suggestions in this regard.

- ✓ First, to regulate, control and ensure stable development of the financial market of Uzbekistan in accordance with the requirements of world practice, as well as to further improve the legal framework for protecting the rights of financial services market participants and investors, and to further liberalize the financial market in accordance with the requirements of world standards, increasing its stability and level of capitalization.
- ✓ Secondly, to promote the transfer of securities trading of corporate structures in the country to secondary markets and strengthen their free placement. In this regard, the first step is to activate the secondary securities market in our country.
- ✓ Secondly, to increase the implementation of operations with derivative financial instruments in the financial market of our country within the framework of the circulation of underlying assets in the real economy or financial markets. In this regard, the introduction of mechanisms for regulating speculative operations with derivative financial instruments. As well as the further development of REPO and SWOP operations in order to regulate liquidity in the financial market.
- ✓ Fourth, further simplify the processes associated with the issuance of securities by commercial banks in our country and increase their attractiveness for issuers and investors, and further improve new types of bank deposits, certificates of deposit and corporate bonds in order to increase the long-term resources of banks.

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that a thorough study of the securities market, which is currently an important and integral part of the world economy, their organization, and the effective mobilization of capital in these markets will ultimately ensure the rapid growth of the country's economy.

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